

Pro-orientation through integration, ecology and geography

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Ключевые слова: содержание, географическая дисциплина, активизирует, дополняет, расширяет, углубляет.

In modern conditions of school work, despite the availability of various variants of ecology programs, there are problems of a new approach to the development of the content of environmental education, which should have not only biological orientation, but also geographical, or more precisely all-round. In order to solve this problem, variation of educational programs provides use of integration courses, ecology, geography and vocational guidance. Knowledge in the field of ecology is necessary for each person in order to understand their role and place in life, in the transformation of reality. Not replacing the teaching of geographical discipline, activates, supplements, expands, deepens the knowledge of students. Gives them a specific practical orientation.

The purposefulness of integration of ecology and geography is beyond doubt. However, knowledge is necessary for each person to realize his role and place in life, in the transformation of reality, to determine an active life position, and this is directly connected with his future profession, its conscious choice.

Therefore, a comprehensive approach in integrating the course is designed to carry out the social order of our society-orientation of school students to their future profession.

Our today's students are tomorrow's industrial and agricultural workers, directors of large corporations, the future of the planet and its ecological purity will depend on them, so our eco-friendly tomorrow depends on what knowledge they get today.

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There is an opinion that in the era of market relations professional orientation has lost its relevance. I do not share such attitudes and believe that it is today that career guidance for students is the most important task of the school, because due to increasing competition and unemployment, the student must be helped to choose a profession in which he could achieve the highest skill, thereby ensuring a sustainable social status. It is possible to become a professional if the right and timely choice of profession is made. The main task is to implement an integrated approach.

The integrated course is a basic, intrasubject course. Since it prepares students for self-education, self-development and self-expression, provides not only training and education, but also the formation of such important personal qualities as intellectual and social activity, diligence, possession of moral norms of behavior and communication, the ability to navigate in nature and the social environment.

Interdisciplinary links constitute the necessary conditions for organizing the educational process as a purposeful system. They act as a means of an integrated approach to learning and strengthening its unity with education. Implementation of interdisciplinary links serves as a didactic condition for its activation, systematization of knowledge, formation of independent thinking and cognitive interest.

The system of students' views on nature, society, and labor are formed on the basis of systematic and multilateral interdisciplinary links in the learning process. Especially important in this respect are connections with the humanities subjects: geography, ecology of all integrations with a professional orientation. Interdisciplinary links increase the scientific level of learning, reflect the natural interconnections of the processes and phenomena of the surrounding world, reveals its material unity. This develops dialectical and systemic thinking of students, flexibility of mind, the ability to transfer and generalize knowledge from different subjects and sciences. Without these intellectual abilities it is impossible to have a

creative attitude to work, to solve modern complex problems in practice that require a synthesis of knowledge from subject areas.

The main link in the educational work at school is the lesson.

Improvement of the methods of studying geography in integration with ecology and vocational guidance needs to begin with

Improving the methodology of the lessons. And not just individual lessons

The improvement of the methods of teaching geography subjects integrated into the ecology and career guidance system starts with improving the methodology of the entire school geography education system. It is necessary to create such a system of lessons which basic task would put formation of geographical concepts in integration with vocational and ecological which, in my opinion, is a logic completion of all work on geography lessons at school which final goal should be to help pupils to master geographical knowledge, to choose a profession, to bring up a specialist capable to carry out industrial activity without damage to the environment.

An effective method of improving geography lessons for integrative purposes is to conduct role-playing games, roundtable discussions, and business games. We often conduct such lessons when summarizing a topic, for example: "Inland waters" - 8th grade, on familiarization with new material, for example "Interrelation of plants, animals, and natural conditions in natural zones of the Russian plain"- 8th grade, etc., "Structure of the Earth" - 6th grade.

These forms of teaching develop students' ability to freely express their opinion, formulate creative activity, determine a personal attitude to the studied object or phenomenon, help deepen environmental and vocational orientation.

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